

EFFECTS OF CHILD ABUSE ON THE GIRL-CHILD IN A RURAL AREA OF RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

This study determined the effects of child abuse on the girl-child in a rural community of Rivers State. This paper specifically considered impaired child development, physical and psychological effects. Study design adopted was descriptive survey. The study population was 852 and sample size of 187 derived. A multi-stage sampling procedure was adopted. The questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection with a reliability index of 0.70. The findings of the study revealed persistent delay in starting school, poor school attendance, inadequate cognitive ability and dropping out of school as the developmental side effects of girl-child abuse. Increased juvenile delinquency in physical injury and recurring body scar were the major physical effects of girl-child abuse; possible entry into a condition of depression, likely rejection by family or loved ones and 'low self-esteem' were the notable effects of girl-child abuse. Therefore, the study recommended that parents/guardians should be advised to avoid acts that will result in girl-child abuse; parents and guardians need to protect their children against any form of child abuse in order to remain free of the mental and physical adverse health effects; and there should be interventions on the part of government, NGOs or individuals in a bid to prevent child abuse on a girl-child.

Keywords: Child abuse, girl-child, effects, impaired development, rural community